

Marianna Charitonidou

Architectural History and Re-inventing Temporal Structures: Beyond Eurocentric

Narratives

At the core of this research project is the idea that Europe as a concept is related to the project of thinking and accomplishing universality. It represents the potential for an enlightened resistance in a world that is progressively becoming dominated by the mono-perspectivism of globalism. In this sense, Eurocentrism is specifiable only within the context of modernity and is crucial for thinking modernity. Taking into account the idea that, as Dipesh Chakrabarty remarks, in *Provincializing Europe: Postcolonial thought and historical difference*, “Europe [...] has already been provincialized by history itself”¹, the chapter places particular emphasis on Reinhart Koselleck’s theory of modernity, in *Futures Past: On the Semantics of Historical Times*². The tendency of architectural historiographies to place Eurocentric narratives under critical scrutiny since the dissolution of colonialist models is accompanied by the questioning of the earlier *Zeitgeist* theories, which had served to legitimize modernism³.

At the centre of this chapter is the idea that both globalization and the digital reproducibility the central issue is the intensification of temporality. The politics of resistance characterizing the endeavours of shaping historiographical methods that try to represent the other go hand in hand with the intention to challenge concepts and historiographies that are based on *Zeitgeist*. As Thomas DaCosta Kaufmann underscores, in “Reflections on World Art History”, “questions about Eurocentrism, and related post-colonial critiques have doubtless had the merit not only of revealing unexamined assumptions, but more positively of attracting attention to overlooked or suppressed points of view and materials”⁴.

During the last four and a half decades, in many cases, the endeavours to incorporate post-colonialist criticism into architectural discourse failed to go beyond the peril of

“provincializing” Europe⁵. By depicting Europe and the West as a homogeneous power of domination over the rest of the world, postcolonial criticism turns Europe into the blind spot of its own discourse. Anthony D. King, in *Writing the Global City: Globalization, Postcolonialism and the Urban*, refers to Homi Bhabha, Edward Said, and Gayatri Spivak’s critique of the “Eurocentricism and the cultural racism of the West”⁶. King also examines the role of postcolonial criticism in decentring “Eurocentric conceptions of the world, not only in terms of society, space and culture, but equally in terms of temporality and history”⁷.

The fallacious character of dichotomies, such as western/non-western or Eurocentric/non-Eurocentric, becomes evident if we bear in mind that various societies have adopted aspects of western modernity without fully adopting them, fitting them into the indigenous culture. The tension between the scientific ethos of the historian’s task, which demands a commitment free of preconceptions and value judgments, and the political function of the project of history, which is based on a certain social order, has always existed since the emergence of the profession of the historian. The objective of the chapter is to explore the place of the aforementioned tension within the framework of the efforts of architectural historians to shape models of architectural historiography that manage to challenge the western canon. An idea on which the reflections that are presented in this chapter are based is the conviction that it is indispensable to avoid labels such as “other” or colonial if we wish to shape architectural history models that challenge the western canon without provincializing it. Particular emphasis is placed on the complicity of architecture with structures of power and dominant ideological agendas in society.

Edmund Husserl’s Theory and the Crisis of European Man

Edmund Husserl’s work and more particularly *The Crisis of European Sciences and*

Transcendental Phenomenology are pivotal for understanding the notion of Europe⁸. The latter was centred on the following question: “Can we live in this world, where historical occurrence is nothing but an unending concatenation of illusory progress and bitter disappointment?”⁹. Among his most significant analyses of the notion of Europe is that presented during a lecture he delivered on 10 May 1935 in Vienna. In this lecture, which was entitled “Philosophy and the Crisis of European Man” and is also known as “The Vienna Lecture”, Husserl argued that “Europe itself [...] [was] [...] in critical condition.”¹⁰ At the core of the reflections he developed during this lecture, he addressed the following question “How is the spiritual image of Europe to be characterized?”¹¹. As he mentioned in his speech the way he used the term did not refer to Europe as a geographic entity, but in a “spiritual sense”, to borrow his own words. More specifically, he understood Europe as “the unity of a spiritual life and a creative activity - with all its aims, interests, cares and troubles, with its plans, its establishments, its institutions”¹². He tried to examine which was “[t]he spiritual image of Europe”¹³ at that specific historical time, referring to a “spiritual telos of European Man”¹⁴.

The problem of Eurocentrism became a historiographic problem in the nineteenth century in line with other concurrent themes such as “exotism,” “orientalism,” “archaeology,” and “culturalism.” As Gevork Hartoonian highlights, in *Crisis of the Object: The Architecture of Theatricality*, “[t]he nineteenth century is famous for its positivism and knowledge of history”¹⁵. Hartoonian also remarks that “the gap between theory and practice was institutionalized”¹⁶ in the nineteenth century, arguing that “modernization had already expanded architects’ horizons of sight and construction”¹⁷ by then.

Sir Bannister Fletcher’s *History of Architecture on the Comparative Method* is a good illustration of the Eurocentric biases of architectural historiography, periodization, and classification.¹⁸ More than forty years before the publication of Sir Bannister Fletcher’s *History*

of *Architecture on the Comparative Method*, James Fergusson published *The Illustrated Handbook of Architecture*, which aimed to provide “a concise and popular account of the different styles of architecture prevailing in all ages and countries.”¹⁹ Fergusson’s three volumes of *A History of Architecture in all Countries, from The Earliest Times to The Present Day* was an attempt to write a comprehensive survey of world architecture.²⁰ Despite his interest in writing about non-Western architecture such as the Indian architecture, as Peter Kohane has remarked, “[c]entral to [...] [Fergusson’s] stereotypical account of the East as Other is the assumed superiority of European civilization.”²¹ Kohane has also noted that Fergusson’s “gaze is that of an enlightened Westerner, who momentarily delights in a strange, confused, and claustrophobic spatial experience, but ultimately remains in control.”²²

Esra Akcanⁱⁿ “Critical Practice in The Global Era: The Question Concerning ‘Other’ Geographies”, tries to examine to what extent “a non-Eurocentric universality is [...] possible.”²³ Akcan’s understanding of universality refers to “a set of values that are perceived to be shared across places and that are nevertheless subject to change”²⁴. Dominic Sachsenmaier, in “Global History and Critiques of Western Perspectives”, analyses, among other issues, the global turn in architectural historiography. A remark of Sachsenmaier, in the aforementioned article, that is useful for exploring how non-Eurocentric architectural historiography models would be possible is his thesis that “transcultural history do not want to continue the Eurocentric paradigms that characterized most of universal history”²⁵.

The Implications of Immanuel Wallerstein’s Critique of Eurocentrism for Historiography

Immanuel Wallerstein, in “Eurocentrism and its Avatars: The Dilemmas of Social Science”, related “non-Eurocentric [...] structure of knowledge [to] [...] a more inclusively

universalist vision of human possibility.”²⁶ In the same article, Wallerstein highlights the necessity to reconsider historiographical methods in order to challenge Eurocentrism. He distinguishes five ways of understanding Eurocentrism in social sciences. The first way has to do with historiography, the second is related to universalism, the third is associated with issues of civilization, the fourth is closely connected with the concept of orientalism and the fifth has to do with progress. The main argument of Wallerstein is that “modern world-system has developed structures of knowledge that are significantly different from previous structures of knowledge”²⁷. Wallerstein maintained that “[w]hat is specific to the structures of knowledge in the world-system is the concept of the ‘two cultures’”, arguing that “[n]o other historical system has instituted a fundamental divorce between science and philosophy/humanities.”²⁸ Esra Akcan, in “Postcolonial Theories in Architecture”, sheds light on “Immanuel Wallerstein’s argument that social science as a discipline has been Eurocentric”²⁹.

As John Agnew argues, in “Immanuel Wallerstein, the “modern world-system,” and radical human geography”, “Eurocentrism is the idea that the world as a whole can be interpreted through the mirror of European experience and how Europeans themselves have understood that.”³⁰ Gregor McLennan, in his article entitled “The Question of Eurocentricism: A Comment on Immanuel Wallerstein”, published in *New Left Review* in 1998, argues that Immanuel Wallerstein’s analysis of Eurocentrism aims to shed light on two dimensions of it: its understanding as “an all-embracing epochal *Weltanschauung*”³¹, on the one hand, and a conception of Eurocentrism as an outcome of the acceptance of Western ideology as dominant, on the other hand. According to McLennan, the first conception of Eurocentrism described above corresponds to his concept of “constitutive geoculture”³². McLennan, in this article, examines this double-fold understanding of Eurocentrism in Wallerstein’s thought, shedding light on his tendency to endorse a “‘gestalt’ approach to Eurocentrism”³³. Wallerstein responded to McLennan’s aforementioned commentary on his theory with an article entitled

“Questioning Eurocentricism: A Reply to Gregor McLennan” also published in the same issue of *New Left Review*³⁴. In his response, he highlighted that “none of us can escape reflecting the epochal Weltanschauung—including non-Europeans—and yet all of us can make serious efforts to analyze the world in a non-Eurocentric manner”³⁵.

Historicising Globalisation: On How to Challenge the Dichotomies Western/non-Western and Eurocentric/non-Eurocentric

Robert Young claims that “total, or, elsewhere, global, history assumes a spatio-temporal continuity between all phenomena, and a certain homogeneity between them insofar as they all express the same form of historicity”³⁶. The task of historicising globalisation goes hand in hand with the questioning of the role of the sources, on the one hand, and with the exploration of the possibilities and limits of the transnational perspective in historical research, on the other³⁷. A seminal book for grasping how historians can challenge Eurocentrism is Peter Gran’s *Beyond Eurocentrism: A New View of Modern World History*, in which the author argues that social history played an important role in the development of the critiques towards Eurocentric models of writing history³⁸.

The notions of place, nation, identity do no longer seem sufficient for architectural historiographies. Useful for establishing non-Eurocentric methods of writing architectural history are the debates about transnational historiography, which focuses on exploring the mutations of ideas through their circulation and their incorporation in different national and institutional concepts. The syncretic dynamic of the ways that urban forms, function as condensed expressions of the conflicts, dialogized or not, between different cultural landscapes, architectural expressions, desires and ideologies is evoked through their unavoidably material representation of the crossings and interactions of the forces that are

involved in their formation.

Architectural and urban historians should try to trust the potential and communicative force of the artifacts to transmit what is in the air a specific moment acting as condensers of the interaction between the social, economic, and political parameters that affect the perception and all the stages of concretization of architectural and urban artifacts from their conception to their materialization. How the movement of people, ideas, technologies, and institutions across national boundaries influences these fractal movements between material expression and textual interpretation and between intention for autonomy and intention for heteronomy? How could the concept of “microphysics of power” (“microphysique du pouvoir”) of Michel Foucault³⁹ and the concept of “micropolitics of desire” (“micropolitique du désir”) of Félix Guattari⁴⁰ contribute to architectural and urban historians’s efforts to grasp these movements of hunting of the concept of progress in the evolution of architecture and urbanism?

To understand how problematic are dichotomies as western/non-western and Eurocentric/non-Eurocentric for architectural historiography, we should not forget that different societies adopted aspects of western modernity without fully adopting them. Gennaro Ascione, in “Unthinking Modernity: Historical-Sociological, Epistemological and Logical Pathways”, tries to reveal the “logical, epistemological and historical-sociological contradictions inherent in the effort to produce non-Eurocentric categories of social and historical analysis”⁴¹. One of the main questions to he intends to respond is whether modernity-Eurocentrism is an indissoluble nexus. He also argues that we should not separate modernity as narration from modernity as *episteme*. The rejection of colonialist models of writing architectural history goes hand in hand with the endeavour of placing Eurocentric narratives and *Zeitgeist* theories under critical scrutiny. In parallel, dichotomies as western/non-western and Eurocentric/non-Eurocentric in architectural history are accompanied by an intention to

scrutinize the interactions between architecture, on the one hand, and structures of power and dominant ideological agendas in the societies under study, on the other.

The task of rethinking the role of Europe in the formation of architectural history models cannot but be related to an institutional analysis of the evolution of architectural history's position within the universities and the production of knowledge at large. Spiro Kostof's *A History of Architecture: Settings and Rituals*, which constitutes an endeavour to include non-monumental and non-western traditions in architectural survey, is interpreted here as an attempt to rethink the western canon. Kostof made a significant effort to present non-western architecture as an important factor in our understanding of western architecture. However, his perspective still remained Eurocentric. On the other hand, Ákos Moravánsky, in *Competing Visions. Aesthetic Invention and Social Imagination in Central European Architecture, 1867-1918*, intended to dissect the tight web of biographical, cultural, and aesthetic cross-connections. For this reason, he chose a thematic structure, which intended to explore architectural history in clusters, rather than through a linear development toward a monolithic modern form. A case that is useful for reflecting on the potentials of different structures is Jean-Louis Cohen's *The Future of Architecture since 1889*⁴², in which the author adopted a narrative structure based on Fernand Braudel's conception of multidimensional "planes"⁴³. Cohen's main objective this book was to incorporate in his historiographical perspective the multiple and overlapping temporalities that characterise the evolution of our understanding of architecture.

Reinhart Koselleck's Overlapping Temporal Layers and Non-*Zeitgeist* Architectural Histories

Apart from the approach of Immanuel Wallerstein concerning the ways in which Eurocentric historiographies can be challenged, Reinhart Koselleck's theory, and more particularly his theory of temporal layers ("Zeitschichten") is also useful for understanding the connections between historiography and temporality⁴⁴. Koselleck argues that since the second half of the eighteenth century "[t]ime is no longer simply the medium in which all histories take place; it gains a historical quality", relating this shift to his conviction that "[t]ime, after this shift, started being treated as] [...] a dynamic and historical force in its own right"⁴⁵.

Koselleck's historiographical approach also aims to challenge the *Zeitgeist*-oriented methods⁴⁶. The approach of Koselleck is based on an understanding of historical times that intends to challenge conventional theories of periodization in history. Koselleck, in the aforementioned book, suggests a "theory of overlapping temporal structure layers, synchronicities and nonsynchronicities"⁴⁷. Two questions concerning the relationship between time and historical narratives that should not be neglected are the following, which are also raised, in *Time in the History of Art Temporality, Chronology, and Anachrony*, by Dan Karlholm and Keith Moxey: "Post-colonial Time Is the chronological system on which art history depends universal? How does it relate to the temporal system of other cultures and can these systems be reconciled?"⁴⁸

Kenneth Frampton, in the introduction of the fifth edition of *Modern Architecture: A Critical History*⁴⁹, that among the first appearances of the term "Modern Architecture" ("Moderne Bewegung") is its use by Otto Wagner, in *Moderne Architektur: Seinen Schülern ein Führer auf diesem Kunstgebiete*⁵⁰. Frampton also mentions that Wagner preferred the title *Die Baukunst unserer Zeit (The Architecture of the Time)* for the 1914 edition of the same book⁵¹. Peter Osborne, in *The Politics of Time: Modernity and Avant-Garde*, argues that the concept of modernity is based on the intention to relate "the contemporaneity of an epoch to

the time of its classification”, registering “this contemporaneity in terms of a qualitatively new, self-transcending temporality which has the simultaneous effect of distancing the present from even that most recent past with which it is thus identified”⁵². Koselleck’s multiple temporalities and “layers of time” is useful for understanding the relationship between modernity and time, as well as the relationship between modernity and space.

Gilles Deleuze, in his book devoted to Michel Foucault, interprets the relation of thought to history, and the connection between the past, the present, and the future in one’s thought as follows: “[t]hought thinks its own history (the past), but in order to free itself from what it thinks (the present) and be able finally to ‘think otherwise’ (the future)”⁵³. Challenging Eurocentric or Western-centric models of architectural historiography is relating to re-inventing how temporal structures when narrating history are conceived. Useful for understanding how both the linear and circular models of how the progress of knowledge in history is narrated in Koselleck’s theory as developed in his seminal book *Futures Past: On the Semantics of Historical Times*. Koselleck argues that the state aimed to controlled the future by “gradually eliminating from the domain of political consideration and decision making the robust religious expectations of the future”⁵⁴. Ute Poerschke, in “Conceptual History and Architectural Theory”, intends to examine how Koselleck’s historiography could enrich architectural history methods⁵⁵. She paid special attention to the insistence of Koselleck in “performing first a synchronic and then a diachronic investigation of a concept”⁵⁶. As Matteo Burioni, in “Naming Things. Terminology, Language Theory and Metaphorology from Alberti to Vignola”, highlights in “[f]ollowing the work of Reinhart Koselleck, Bernhard Jussen and Jaques Guilhaumou, a history of architectural concepts could be realised”⁵⁷. The emergence of modernity is related to the reconceptualization of temporality. Koselleck’s theory of multiple times would be useful for understanding the shift concerning modernity in architecture.

-
- ¹ D. Chakrabarty, *Provincializing Europe: Postcolonial thought and historical difference* (Princeton, N.J.: Princeton University Press, 2009), p. 3.
- ² R. Koselleck, *Futures Past: On the Semantics of Historical Times*, trans. Keith Tribe (New York: Columbia University Press, 2004); R. Koselleck, *Vergangene Zukunft: Zur Semantik geschichtlicher Zeiten* (Frankfurt/Main: Suhrkamp, 1979).
- ³ M. Charitonidou, “Rethinking Europe’s Position in the Formation of Architectural Histories: Is a Non-Eurocentric Narrative Possible?”, III Congreso Internacional AhAU “Built and Thought: European and Transatlantic Correspondence in the Historiography of Architecture”, 1-3 June 2022, Madrid, Spain, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3929/ethz-b-000480884>; M. Charitonidou, “Towards Non-Eurocentric Historiographies: Challenging Europe’s Position in the Formation of Architectural Histories”, 7th Biannual Conference of the European Architectural History Network (EAHN 2022), 15–18 June 2022, Madrid, Spain, <https://doi.org/10.3929/ethz-b-000524602>
- ⁴ T. DaCosta Kaufmann, “Reflections on World Art History”, in T. DaCosta Kaufmann, C. Dossin, B. Joyeux-Prunel, eds., *Circulations in the Global History of Art* (London; New York: Routledge, 2016), p. 28.
- ⁵ Chakrabarty, *Provincializing Europe: Postcolonial thought and historical difference*.
- ⁶ A. D. King, *Writing the Global City: Globalization, Postcolonialism and the Urban* (New York: Routledge, 2016), p. 41.
- ⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 69.
- ⁸ T. Miettinen, *Husserl and the Idea of Europe* (Evanston, IL: Northwestern University Press, 2020); E. Husserl, *The Crisis of European Sciences and Transcendental Phenomenology: An Introduction to Phenomenological Philosophy* (Evanston, IL: Northwestern University Press, 1970).
- ⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 7.
- ¹⁰ E. Husserl” Philosophy and the Crisis of European Man”, Lecture delivered by Edmund Husserl, Vienna, 10 May 1935; this lecture is often referred to as “The Vienna Lecture”, http://www.markfoster.net/struc/philosophy_and_the_crisis_of_european_man.pdf
- ¹¹ *Ibid.*
- ¹² *Ibid.*
- ¹³ *Ibid.*
- ¹⁴ *Ibid.*
- ¹⁵ G. Hartoonian, *Crisis of the Object: The Architecture of Theatricality* (London; New York: Routledge, 2006), p. 159.
- ¹⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 19.
- ¹⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 73.

-
- ¹⁸ Sir Banister Fletcher, *History of Architecture on the Comparative Method* (London: B.T. Batsford Ltd., 1896); John Mckean, “Sir Banister Fletcher: Pillar to post-colonial readings”, *The Journal of Architecture*, 11(2) (2006), 187–204, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13602360600786126>
- ¹⁹ J. Fergusson, *The Illustrated Handbook of Architecture: Being a Concise and Popular Account of the Different Styles of Architecture Prevailing in All Ages and Countries*, 2 vols (London: John Murray, 1855).
- ²⁰ J. Fergusson, *A History of Architecture in All Countries: From the Earliest Times to the Present Day*, Vol. I, Vol. II, Vol. III (London: John Murray, 1862-1867).
- ²¹ J. Fergusson, *History of Indian and Eastern Architecture* (London: John Murray, 1876).
- ²² P. Kohane, “From Scotland to India: The Sources of James Fergusson’s Theory of Architecture’s ‘True Styles’”, *ABE Journal*, 14-15 (2019), doi: <https://doi.org/10.4000/abe.5551>
- ²³ E. Akcan, “Critical Practice in The Global Era: The Question Concerning ‘Other’ Geographies”, *Architectural Theory Review*, 7(1) (2002): 37-57, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13264820209478443>
- ²⁴ Ibid.
- ²⁵ D. Sachsenmaier, “Global History and Critiques of Western Perspectives”, in Ross E. Dunn, Laura J. Mitchell, Kerry Ward, eds., *The New World History. A Field Guide for Teachers and Researchers* (California: University of California Press, 2016), p. 456; D. Sachsenmaier, “Global history and critiques of western perspectives”, *Comparative Education*, 42(3) (2006): 451-470, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03050060600876780>
- ²⁶ I. Wallerstein, “Eurocentrism and its Avatars: The Dilemmas of Social Science”, *Sociological Bulletin*, 46(1) (1997): 21-39, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038022919970102>; see also I. Wallerstein, *The Modern World-System, vol. 1, Capitalist Agriculture and the Origins of the European World-Economy in the Sixteenth Century* (New York; London: Academic Press, 1974); I. Wallerstein, *The Modern World-System, vol. 2, Mercantilism and the Consolidation of the European World-Economy, 1600–1750* (New York: Academic Press, 1980).
- ²⁷ Ibid., p. 37.
- ²⁸ Ibid.
- ²⁹ E. Akcan, “Postcolonial Theories in Architecture”, in E. G. Haddad, D. Rifkind, eds., *A Critical History of Contemporary Architecture 1960–2010* (London; New York: Routledge, 2016), p. 116.
- ³⁰ J. Agnew, “Immanuel Wallerstein, the “modern world-system,” and radical human geography”, *Human Geography*, 14(1) (2021): 17–30, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1942778620974056>
- ³¹ G. McLennan, “The Question of Eurocentricism: A Comment on Immanuel Wallerstein”, *New Left Review*, 1(231) (1998), <https://newleftreview.org/issues/i231/articles/gregor-mclennan-the-question-of-eurocentricism-a-comment-on-immanuel-wallerstein>
- ³² Ibid.
- ³³ Ibid.

-
- ³⁴ I. Wallerstein, “Questioning Eurocentricism: A Reply to Gregor McLennan”, *New Left Review*, 1(231) (1998), <https://newleftreview.org/issues/i231/articles/immanuel-wallerstein-questioning-eurocentricism-a-reply-to-gregor-mclennan>
- ³⁵ Ibid.
- ³⁶ R. Young, *White Mythologies: Writing History and the West* (London; New York: Routledge, 2004), p. 114.
- ³⁷ M. Charitonidou, “Réinventer la posture historique: les débats théoriques à propos de la comparaison et des transferts”, *Espaces et Sociétés*, 167 (2016): 137-152, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3917/esp.167.0137>
- ³⁸ P. Gran, *Beyond Eurocentrism: A New View of Modern World History* (Syracuse, NY: Syracuse University Press, 1996).
- ³⁹ M. Foucault, *Power: Essential Works of Foucault, 1954-1984*, translated by R. Hurley, edited by J. D. Faubion (New York: The New Press, 2001).
- ⁴⁰ F. Guattari, “Microphysics of Power/Micropolitics of Desire”, in G. Genosko, ed., *The Guattari Reader*, translated by John Caruana (Oxford: Blackwell, 1996), p. 178.
- ⁴¹ G. Ascione, in “Unthinking Modernity: Historical-Sociological, Epistemological and Logical Pathways”, *Journal of Historical Sociology*, 27(4) (2014): 463-489, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/johs.12042>
- ⁴² J.-L. Cohen, *The Future of Architecture since 1889* (London: Phaidon Press, 2012).
- ⁴³ F. Braudel, *On History*, translated by Sarah Matthews (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1980).
- ⁴⁴ H. Schulz-Forberg, “The spatial and temporal layers of global history: a reflection on global conceptual history through expanding Reinhart Koselleck's Zeitschichten into global spaces”, *Historical Social Research*, 38(3) (2013), 40-58, doi: <https://doi.org/10.12759/hsr.38.2013.3.40-58>
- ⁴⁵ Koselleck, *Futures Past: On the Semantics of Historical Times*, p. 236.
- ⁴⁶ Ibid.
- ⁴⁷ H. Jordheim, “Against Periodization: Koselleck’s Theory of Multiple Temporalities”, *History and Theory*, 51(2) (2012): 151-171.
- ⁴⁸ D. Karlholm, K. Moxey, “Introduction: Telling Art’s Time”, in D. Karlholm, K. Moxey, eds., *Time in the History of Art Temporality, Chronology, and Anachrony* (London; New York: Routledge, 2018), p. 4.
- ⁴⁹ K. Frampton, *Modern Architecture: A Critical History (World of Art)* (London: Thames and Hudson, 2020).
- ⁵⁰ O. Wagner, *Moderne Architektur: Seinen Schülern ein Führer auf diesem Kunstgebiete* (Vienna: Anton Schroll, 1896); O. Wagner, *Modern Architecture: A Guide of his Students to this Field of Art*, trans. H. F. Mallgrave (Santa Monica, CA: Getty Publications, 1988).
- ⁵¹ O. Wagner, *Die Baukunst unserer Zeit* (Vienna: Schroll, 1914).

⁵² P. Osborne, *The Politics of Time: Modernity and Avant-Garde* (London; New York: Verso, 1995).

⁵³ G. Deleuze, *Foucault*, trans. Seán Hand, foreword by Paul Bové (London; Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2006), p. 119.

⁵⁴ Koselleck, *Futures Past: On the Semantics of Historical Times*, p. 16.

⁵⁵ U. Poerschke, “Conceptual History and Architectural Theory”, in P. Feldhusen, Sebastian, U. Poerschke, eds., *Theorie der Architektur: Zeitgenössische Positionen* (Berlin, Boston: Birkhäuser, 2017), 158-177.

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*, p. 169.

⁵⁷ M. Burioni, in “Naming Things. Terminology, Language Theory and Metaphorology from Alberti to Vignola”, in A. Gerber, B. Patterson, eds., *Metaphors in Architecture and Urbanism: An Introduction* (Bielefeld: transcript Verlag, 2013), p. 83.